

SOLUBILITY AND DISSOLUTION ENHANCEMENT OF ZIPRASIDONE BY BINARY AND TERNARY SOLID DISPERSION

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The objective of this research was to improve the solubility and dissolution rate of Ziprasidone by binary and ternary solid dispersion technique. **Methods:** Solid dispersions were prepared by physical mixture and solvent evaporation in the binary and ternary system. In binary system Ziprasidone was mixed with PEG 6000 in the ratio of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 and with β -Cyclodextrin in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 ratio. In ternary system Ziprasidone was prepared with PEG 6000 and β -Cyclodextrin in the ratio of 1:1:1, 1:2:1, 1:3:1, 1:1:2 and 1:1:3. Pure Ziprasidone, solid dispersions, and physical mixtures were characterized by FT-IR, drug content and dissolution testing. **Results:** FTIR studies confirm that there was no interaction between drug and carriers used in the preparation of solid dispersion. The results of drug content uniformity study show the uniform dispersion of Ziprasidone throughout the formulation. Preparation of ternary solid dispersion enhanced

the dissolution of the drug compared to the pure drug and binary system. Among the various formulations prepared, Dissolution efficiency with formulation (T5) was higher than that obtained with binary solid dispersions containing the same proportion of either PEG or β -cyclodextrin. **Conclusion:** Overall the results of research work reveals that when Ziprasidone

was formulated as an ternary system shows higher solubility, faster dissolution rate, which may enhances the bioavailability.

KEYWORDS: Ziprasidone, Solid dispersions, PEG 6000, β -Cyclodextrin.

INTRODUCTION

The number of poor water soluble or lipophilic active pharmaceuticals ingredients (API) has risen sharply in recent years and formulation of such entities presents greater challenges to formulation and research pharmacists.^[1] As a matter of fact, more than 40% of new chemical entities are insufficiently soluble to allow for acceptable dosage formulation. In the last decade, competition in the pharmaceutical area has revolved around improving physicochemical properties of drugs and improving formulations to give the patient a better and effective product.^[2] The knowledge of Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS) included in the guidelines of the U.S.F.D.A (food and drug administration), can be utilized by the formulation scientists for developing an optimized dosage form. Along with the permeability, the dissolution of drug in gastro-intestinal fluid is a key factor in the determination of its oral bioavailability.^[3] Drug dissolution from oral solid dosage forms depends on the release of a drug from the dosage form and subsequent solubilization of drug particles in physiological fluid. For poorly soluble, the rate of oral absorption is often controlled by the dissolution rate in the gastrointestinal tract. Therefore together with the permeability, the solubility and dissolution behavior of a drug are key determinants of its oral bioavailability.^[4, 5]

Consideration of the modified Noyes-Whitney equation provides some hints as to how the dissolution rate of even very poorly soluble compounds might be improved to minimize to oral availability.^[6,7]

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{AD(C_s - C)}{h}$$

Where, dC/dt = rate of dissolution, A = surface area available for dissolution, D = diffusion co-efficient of the compound, C_s = solubility of compound in dissolution medium, C = concentration of drug in medium at time 't', h = thickness of diffusion boundary layer adjacent to the surface of the dissolving compound. To increase the dissolution rate according to the above equation, the following approaches are available, to increase the surface area available for dissolution by decreasing the particle size of drug, optimizing the wetting characteristics

of compound surface. To decrease the boundary layer thickness, Ensure sink condition for dissolution, Improve apparent solubility of drug under physiologically relevant conditions. Among the above four approaches, the most attractive option for increasing the release rate is the improvement of the solubility through various formulation approaches.

Solid dispersions systems as ‘the dispersion of one or more active ingredients in an inert carrier matrix at solid-state prepared by the melting (fusion), solvent or melting-solvent method’, while Corrigan suggested the definition as being a ‘product formed by converting a fluid drug-carrier combination to the solid state.’^[8, 9] Dispersions obtained through the fusion process are often called as melts and those obtained by solvent method are frequently referred to as co-precipitates or co-evaporates. Thermodynamically, such system is an intimately blended physical mixture of its two crystalline components. The X-ray diffraction pattern of a eutectic mixture constitutes an additive composite of the two components.

An inclusion complex is a unique form of inclusion chemical complex in which one molecule is enclosed within another molecule or structure of molecules. The combination is characterized by absence of ordinary chemical bonds, the essential criteria is that enclosed molecule or guest be of a suitable size and shape to fit into a cavity within a solid structure formed by a host molecule. The stereochemistry and possibly the polarity of both host and guest molecules determine whether the inclusion complex can occur. The resulting close fit of the two components produces a combination of significant strength due to total dispersion force between interacting components. This type of spatial complex does not occur by means of ionic, covalent or coordinate covalent bond but is dependent upon dispersion forces and possibly highly oriented dipoles for stability differing greatly from chemical complexation. Inclusion complexes were first observed by Mylius in Hydroquinone and several other volatile compounds. He proposed that two chemical components were interacting without chemical bonding and suggested one molecule was enclosed into another. X-ray studies confirmed those studies showing formation of Cage-like structure.^[10]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

All of the chemicals and reagents used in this study were of analytical reagent (AR), laboratory reagent (LR), or the highest grade available in the lab, and they were utilized exactly as supplied, requiring no additional purification. A gift sample of ziprasidone was

acquired from Optimus Drug Pvt. Ltd. in India. Methanol, β -Cyclodextrin, and Polyethylene Glycol 6000 were purchased from S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd. in Mumbai, India.

Instruments

A UV–Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-Vis 1700) for spectrophotometric analysis, a USP XXIII dissolution rate test apparatus (Electrolab Electronics) for dissolution studies, an Acculab electronic balance for precise material weighing, a hot air oven (M.C. Dalal and Co., Chennai) for drying, and a vortex mixer (Kemi Electricals) for appropriate solution mixing were among the tools utilized in this work.

Determination of Melting Point

Melting point of Ziprasidone was determined using digital melting point apparatus by Capillary method.^[11]

Compatibility study

Fourier Transform Infra-Red spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectra help to confirm the identity of drug and to detect the interaction of the drug with the carriers. IR spectroscopy of pure drug and physical mixture of drug with polymers was carried out using Shimadzu FTIR to check the compatibility between drug and polymers. The IR spectra of drug with polymers were compared with the standard IR spectrum of the pure drug.^[12]

Standard curve of ziprasidone in distilled water^[13]

Preparation of standard stock solution

Stock solution of standard drug samples was prepared by dissolving 10mg of Ziprasidone in small quantity of methanol in 100ml of volumetric flask, and then the volume was made up to 100ml with methanol (stock solution 1).

Determination of λ max of Ziprasidone

Above stock solution was scanned between the wavelengths of 200-400nm which give a highest peak and same was selected for Ziprasidone as λ max shown in the figure no. 5.

Preparation of calibration curve of Ziprasidone

From the above stock solution series of dilutions were made to get 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 μ g/ml solutions using methanol and correspondence absorbance was measured using UV visible

spectrophotometer. A standard graph was drawn using the average value of six trials and it is shown in figure no. 6.

Phase Solubility Study^[14]

Phase solubility study was performed according to the method described by Higuchi and Connors. Ziprasidone in excess amounts was added to 25 ml of different concentrations of PEG 6000 and β -Cyclodextrin in glass stoppered flasks respectively. The Ziprasidone with PEG 6000 and β -Cyclodextrin in different ratios (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3) were used. Flasks were placed in thermostatically controlled shaking water bath for 72 hr at 37°C. After equilibrium, aliquots were withdrawn then passed through a millipore filter (0.45 μ m Sartorius, AG Germany), then analyzed using a UV-visible spectrophotometer after suitable dilution. All the data were the average of three determinations.

Preparation of binary solid dispersion^[15]

Solid dispersions containing Ziprasidone binary and ternary systems have been prepared by physical mixture and solvent evaporation method, according to the drug-polymer ratios presented in table 1 and 2.

Preparation of physical mixture

Physical mixtures (PMs) having the three different mass ratios (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3) were prepared by thoroughly mixing appropriate amounts of Ziprasidone and PEG 6000 or β -Cyclodextrin in a mortar until a homogeneous mixture was obtained. The resulting mixtures were sieved through a 100 # sieve and stored in desiccator until use.

Binary and Ternary Solid dispersions prepared by solvent evaporation method

SDs of Ziprasidone in PEG 6000 or β -Cyclodextrin containing three different mass ratios (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3) respectively were prepared by the solvent evaporation method as follows. Ziprasidone in the appropriate amount of PEG 6000 or β -Cyclodextrin was dissolved in organic solvent methanol (25 ml). In ternary solid dispersions, Ziprasidone was incorporated into PEG 6000 and β -Cyclodextrin to obtain the dispersions with weight ratios of 1:1:1, 1:2:1, 1:3:1, 1:1:2, 1:1:3, (Ziprasidone/PEG6000/ β -Cyclodextrin). After entire solubility, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure at 40°C and the resulting residue was dried under vacuum for 3 h, and stored in a desiccator for at least overnight, ground in a mortar, and passed through a 100 # sieve.

Table-1: Formulation of Binary solid dispersion.

Solid dispersion	Formulation Code	Drug-Polymer Ratio	Method
PEG-6000	PMPEG1	1:1	Physical mixture
	PMPEG2	1:2	
	PMPEG3	1:3	
	SEPEG1	1:1	Solvent evaporation
	SEPEG2	1:2	
	SEPEG3	1:3	
β -Cyclodextrin	PM β -CD1	1:1	Physical mixture
	PM β -CD2	1:2	
	PM β -CD3	1:3	
	SE β -CD1	1:1	Solvent evaporation
	SE β -CD2	1:2	
	SE β -CD3	1:3	

Table-2: Formulation of Ternary solid dispersion.

Ternary System	Code	Drug-Polymer ratio	Method
Drug:PEG6000: β -Cyclodextrin	T1	1:1:1	Solvent evaporation
	T2	1:2:1	
	T3	1:3:1	
	T4	1:1:2	
	T5	1:1:3	

Evaluation of Solid dispersions**Percentage Practical Yield**

Percentage practical yield was calculated to know about percent yield or efficiency of any method, thus its help in selection of appropriate method of production. Solid dispersions were collected and weighed to determine practical yield (PY) from the following equation.^[16]

		Practical Mass (Solid dispersion)	
PY (%)		-----	x 100
		Theoretical Mass (Drug+ Carrier)	

Drug content estimation

The solid dispersion equivalent to 10 mg of the drug was accurately weighed and transferred to 100 mL volumetric flask. 20ml methanol was added and continuously shaken for 10 min and final volume was made up to the mark with methanol. After suitable dilutions the solution was filtered through 0.45 μ m millipore filters and the absorbance was measured at respective wavelength using methanol as blank. Each study was done in triplicate.^[17]

***In-vitro* dissolution studies**

In vitro dissolution study of Ziprasidone binary and ternary systems and pure drug was performed in a paddle-type dissolution apparatus USP II Dissolution tester (Electro lab) equilibrated at $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 50 rpm speed. The dissolution study was carried out in triplicate for one hour in 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl. Dissolution samples 5 ml were collected at 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, and 60 min and replaced with an equal volume of 0.1 N HCl to maintain the volume constant. The sample solution was filtered and analyzed by a UV/VIS spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800) at 317 nm.^[16]

Stability Study^[18]

Stability of a dosage form has been defined as the ability of a particular formulation in a specific container to remain within its physical, chemical, therapeutic and toxicological specification. Accelerated stability study was carried out as per the ICH guidelines.

Procedure

As per ICH guidelines, optimized solid dispersion (T5) was subjected to accelerated stability studies. Optimized solid dispersion were kept in zip lock pouch and exposed to controlled temperature ($40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and RH ($75\pm 5\%$) for a period of 3 months in humidity control oven. After 30, 60 and 90 days, the sample were taken out and analyzed for physical appearance and drug content.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Melting Point of Ziprasidone

The melting point was found near to 275°C . Hence, experimental values were in good agreement with official value. Thus obtained melting point is in agreement with literature melting point, confirming the purity of drug.

Drug Excipients Compatibility Studies

Fourier Transform Infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR)

Table 3: Major peaks of Ziprasidone in FT-IR spectra.

Formulation code	N=O Stretching	C=C stretching	S=O Stretchig	C-O Stretching
Pure drug	2934.67	1626.16	1270.87	1014.35
Physical mixture of drug+PEG6000	2901.95	1631.02	1281.70	1019.42
Physical mixture of drug+PVP	2901.68	1630.90	1281.63	1019.48

Physical mixture of drug+PEG6000+PVP	2901.89	1631.02	1281.70	1019.54
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Fig. 1: FT-IR of Ziprasidone

Fig. 2: FT-IR of Drug + PEG 6000

Fig. 3: FT-IR of Drug + β-Cyclodextrin

Fig. 4: FT-IR of Drug + PEG + β-Cyclodextrin

Determination of λ Max

Suitable analytical method was developed for Ziprasidone using UV spectrophotometer. Analytical wavelength of λ max 317 nm for Ziprasidone was identified in methanol as shown in Fig 5

Fig. 5: Analytical wavelength of Ziprasidone.

Standard calibration curve of ziprasidone

Table-4: Standard Calibration data of Ziprasidone.

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance AM \pm SD
1.	0	0
2.	10	0.157 \pm 0.032
3.	20	0.298 \pm 0.028
4.	30	0.442 \pm 0.067
5.	40	0.599 \pm 0.040
6.	50	0.741 \pm 0.065

Fig. 6: Standard Calibration curve of Ziprasidone.

Phase solubility study

Table-5: Phase solubility study of Ziprasidone.

Method	Ratio	Solubility ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Pure drug	1:0	0.62 \pm 0.75
Drug+PEG 6000	1:1	6.49 \pm 1.11
	1:2	10.68 \pm 2.13
	1:3	13.65 \pm 1.63
	1:1	7.61 \pm 1.18
Drug+ β -cyclodextrin	1:2	12.85 \pm 1.16
	1:3	14.80 \pm 2.66

Drug Content

Table 6: Percentage Yield and drug content of Binary and ternary systems.

Solid dispersion	Formulation Code	Drug-Polymer Ratio	% Yield	Drug content %
PEG-6000	PMPEG1	1:1	75	77.0 \pm 2.83
	PMPEG2	1:2	87	88.0 \pm 0.55
	PMPEG1	1:3	90.5	90.5 \pm 1.26
	SEPEG1	1:1	65	73.0 \pm 1.82
	SEPEG2	1:2	80	86.6 \pm 2.13
	SEPEG3	1:3	90	88.5 \pm 2.83
β -Cyclodextrin	PMPVP1	1:1	65	70.0 \pm 1.66
	PMPVP2	1:2	85	96.6 \pm 1.54
	PMPVP3	1:3	89.1	95.0 \pm 1.90

	SEPVP1	1:1	85	72.0± 2.11
	SEPVP2	1:2	70	93.3± 0.84
	SEPVP3	1:3	80	97.5± 0.74
Ternary systems				
Drug:PEG6000: β-Cyclodextrin	T1	1:1:1	88.62	82.06± 1.26
	T2	1:2:1	84.33	86.28± 1.19
	T3	1:3:1	80.72	84.32± 0.22
	T4	1:1:2	92.38	89.76± 1.41
	T5	1:1:3	94.55	93.11± 1.66

In-Vitro Dissolution Studies

Table-7: Dissolution data of pure Ziprasidone binary solid dispersion prepared using PEG 6000.

Time (min)	Cumulative % drug release (AM ± SD)						
	Pure drug	PMPEG1	PMPEG2	PMPEG3	SEPEG1	SEPEG2	SEPEG3
0	0.00	0 ± 0.00	0 ± 0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00
5	10.4	4.15±2.80	6.78±2.85	8.06±3.99	10.52±2.12	12.68±2.01	15.88±1.49
10	15.16	17.60±1.71	23.32±3.32	29.44±2.34	32.18±1.12	38.83±2.78	39.50±3.07
20	21.35	27.49±2.12	40.13±1.12	43.83±2.02	47.02±2.91	50.66±1.25	55.72±5.90
30	27.50	40.45±2.89	66.35±1.97	69.25±3.36	65.03±3.15	76.08±4.45	78.42±2.73
45	36.82	58.65±3.42	72.61±3.09	77.08±3.38	80.59±5.48	83.19±6.13	85.56±4.8
60	48.65	78.48±1.71	84.72±2.02	89.92±3.15	82.40±2.91	86.47±1.49	88.69±2.85

Table-8: Dissolution data of pure Ziprasidone binary solid dispersion prepared by using β-Cyclodextrin.

Time (min)	Cumulative % drug release (AM ± SD)						
	Pure drug	PMβ-CD1	PEβ-CD2	PMβ-CD3	SEβ-CD1	SEβ-CD2	SEβ-CD3
0	0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00
5	10.4	6.30±2.31	9.32±2.64	10.44±1.06	16.03±2.12	18.83±2.12	21.88±1.49
10	15.16	19.60±2.26	26.13±1.88	31.83±2.07	36.18±1.12	40.66±2.79	42.50±3.07
20	21.35	30.49±1.54	41.35±2.82	47.25±3.08	50.02±2.91	55.08±1.25	59.72±5.90
30	27.50	43.47±2.26	68.61±2.94	71.08±2.66	68.03±3.15	78.19±4.45	84.42±2.73
45	36.82	60.65±2.02	79.21±2.96	79.92±2.41	83.59±5.48	87.47±6.18	89.56±4.85
60	48.65	81.48±2.12	86.72±2.26	91.69±1.11	84.40±2.91	90.60±2.62	92.69±2.10

Fig. 7: Dissolution Profile of pure Ziprasidone binary solid dispersion prepared by using PEG 6000

Fig. 8: Dissolution Profile of pure Ziprasidone binary solid dispersion prepared by using β-Cyclodextrin

Table-9: Dissolution Profile of Ziprasidone ternary system prepared by Solvent evaporation method.

Time (min)	Cumulative % drug release (AM ± SD)				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
0	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00	0±0.00
10	21.35±2.36	29.81±2.51	28.22±4.80	36.31±0.48	42.47±3.04
20	34.31±1.29	46.82±1.08	48.88±4.84	52.60±0.50	66.45±3.84
30	66.61±1.35	74.17±4.09	72.20±1.12	78.22±0.46	92.80±5.06

Fig. 9: Dissolution Profile of ternary system.

Stability Studies

Table-10: Stability study of optimized formulation T5.

Time (month)	Entrapment efficiency (%)
Zero	93.11± 1.66
First	93.02± 1.42
Second	92.88± 1.08
Third	92.72± 1.86

Solid dispersion of Ziprasidone was developed with an aim to enhancement of solubility and dissolution. Ziprasidone solid dispersions were developed with a view to deliver the drug in the schizophrenia, bipolar disorder to achieve fast onset of action.^[19] The proper design and formulation of a dosage forms required consideration of the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of all drug substances and excipients used in fabricating the final products. The stable and effective solid dosage forms depend on the careful selection of the excipients that are added in the formulations.^[20,21] The drug and excipients must be compatible with one another to produce a product that is stable, efficacious and safe. The possible interaction between the drug and the carrier was studied by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimeter. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy has been used to assess the interaction between carrier and drug molecule. FTIR spectrum of pure drug, and physical mixture of drug and polymer are shown in Figure No 1-4 respectively. There are no considerable changes in the IR peaks of mixture of drug and excipients when compared to pure Ziprasidone. These observations indicated the absence of interaction between drug and excipients used in the solid dispersions as shown in table no 4. The results of saturation solubility studies are given in table no. 5. The solubility of pure drug in 0.1N HCl was found to be $0.62 \pm 0.75 \mu\text{g/mL}$. The solubility of physical mixture prepared using PEG 4000 in the ratio (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3) was $6.49 \pm 1.11 \mu\text{g/mL}$, $10.68 \pm 2.13 \mu\text{g/mL}$, and $13.65 \pm 1.63 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively in 0.1N HCl. The solubility of physical mixture prepared using β -cyclodextrin in the ratio (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3) 0.1N HCl was found to be $7.61 \pm 1.18 \mu\text{g/mL}$, $12.85 \pm 1.16 \mu\text{g/mL}$, $14.80 \pm 2.66 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. From this, it can be seen that the apparent solubility of Ziprasidone increased with increased in carrier concentrations. Both carriers show an increased solubility of Ziprasidone. Binary and ternary solid dispersions were prepared using different ratios of drug with PEG 6000 or drug with β -cyclodextrin and drug with PEG 6000 and β -Cyclodextrin are listed in Table 7 and 8. The percentage yields of all binary and ternary systems are shown in Table 6. The percentage yield increased with increase in the concentration of polymer. High values of the percentage yield are the strong indication that the formulation technique adopted is reliable and amenable to validation, consistent with similar reports. Physical mixture and solid dispersions showed the presence of good drug content with low standard deviation. It indicates that drug was uniformly dispersed in the powder formulation. Therefore, the method used in this study appears to be reproducible for the preparation of solid dispersion. Dissolution profiles of Ziprasidone in pure state or in binary and ternary solid dispersions. The dissolution data values are presented in table 9. The dissolution results revealed poor and slow dissolution of pure Ziprasidone.

Ziprasidone binary solid dispersion with either PEG 6000 or β -Cyclodextrin resulted in significant enhancement of Ziprasidone dissolution. This is revealed from the significant increase in the dissolution efficiencies (DE%) compared to the pure drug. The DE% of the drug was increased by increasing the proportion of PEG or β -Cyclodextrin in the binary system. The data revealed a trend of higher efficiency for β -Cyclodextrin compared to that recorded in case of PEG 6000 systems. This was evident when comparing the corresponding binary systems with respect to their dissolution efficiencies. Preparation of ternary solid dispersion enhanced the dissolution of the drug compared to the pure drug and binary system. The ternary solid dispersion T5 (1:1:3; drug : PEG : β -Cyclodextrin) resulted in an ideal dissolution profile with more than 90% of the drug being released in the 30 minutes. Dissolution efficiency with this formulation (T5) was higher than that obtained with binary solid dispersions containing the same proportion of either PEG or β -Cyclodextrin. All the regulatory bodies accept only real time stability data for any drug or pharmaceutical for the purpose of accessing shelf life and accelerated stability studies may only serve as tool for formulation screening and stability issue related to shipping or storage at room temperature. On storage, the optimized ternary solid dispersion (T5) did not show any change in physical properties and as well as no remarkable change in the drug content profile as indicated in the table no. 6 which were in the acceptable range. At the end of 90 days, the optimized formulation (T5) was fairly stable at accelerated storage condition.

CONCLUSION

This study was started to establish the possibility of preparing solid dispersions with improved aqueous solubility and dissolution rate, which will solve the difficulties in the development of pharmaceutical dosage forms of Ziprasidone. FT-IR and DSC studies indicated no interaction between drug and carrier. The drug was completely miscible in water-soluble carrier. Preparation of solid binary and ternary solid dispersion of Ziprasidone with PEG 6000 and β -Cyclodextrin significantly enhanced the dissolution rate of the drug compared to the pure drug. The ternary system containing the drug with PEG 6000 and β -Cyclodextrin (1:1:3) was the most effective with more than 90% of the drug being released within 30 minutes. The mechanisms responsible for this improvement could be a solubilization effect of the carrier, miscibility of the drug in carrier, and may be conversion of the drug from crystalline to amorphous form.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict of interest.

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